
E-Commerce's Effects on the Indian Economy

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Abstract:

E-commerce is the exchange of money or information using an electronic network, usually the Internet, for the purchase and sale of goods and services. These business interactions take place between businesses and consumers, or between consumers and businesses. E-business and e-commerce are frequently used interchangeably. Transactional processes related to online retail are also occasionally referred to by the term "e-tail." Technologies including supply chain management, online marketing, mobile commerce, electronic fund transfers, online transaction processing, electronic data interchange, inventory management software, and data collecting systems are all used in e-commerce. Email, fax, online catalogues and shopping carts, Electronic Data Interchange, File Transfer Protocol, and Web services are just a few of the tools used in e-commerce. Company to company accounts for the majority of this, with some Businesses are trying to send out e-newsletters to subscribers and deliver unsolicited advertisements to customers and other business prospects via fax and email. In India, e-commerce is a developing industry. Similar to how the Indian IT sector expanded throughout the 1990s, the 2010s will be recognised for the expansion of the e-commerce sector. E-commerce currently contributes around 0.2% of GDP, but by 2030, it is predicted to have increased 15 times to about 2.5%. The impact is so great that without e-commerce, the current wave of demonetisation would not have been possible. E-commerce both benefited the most from it and, to a considerable measure, helped absorb its impact. By 2030 it is anticipated that e-commerce will contribute approximately \$300 billion to the GDP, or \$20 billion in its current form.

Keywords: E- Commerce, Interchangeably, Transactional, Accessibility, Perceived.

Introduction:

Online purchasing or selling is known as e-commerce. Mobile commerce, electronic funds transfers, supply chain management, Internet marketing, online transaction processing, electronic data exchange (EDI), inventory management systems, and automated data gathering systems are just a few of the technologies that are used in electronic commerce. Although it may also employ other technologies like email, modern electronic commerce usually leverages the World Wide

Web for at least one aspect of the transaction life cycle.

E-commerce businesses may employ some or all of the following:

- Online shopping portals for direct retail sales to customers
- Offering or taking part in online marketplaces that handle sales between third-party businesses and consumers or between consumers
- Business-to-business sales and purchases

- Collecting and utilising demographic information from social media and online interactions
- Interchange of electronic data between businesses (B2B)
- Marketing to both current and potential clients via fax or email (e.g., newsletters)
- Participating in the introduction of new goods and services
- Online financial exchanges for trading or currency exchange

The Federal Trade Commission (FTC) in the United States regulates a number of electronic commerce activities. These activities include, but are not limited to, internet advertising, consumer privacy, and the use of commercial emails. All types of advertising, including internet advertising, are governed by the Federal Trade Commission Act, which mandates that advertisements be honest and non-deceptive. The FTC has brought several cases to enforce the claims made in business privacy statements, especially those regarding the protection of consumers' personal information, using its authority under Section 5 of the FTC Act, which forbids unfair or deceptive conduct. The FTC may therefore enforce any corporate privacy policy pertaining to e-commerce activities. The Consumer Protection Act of 2008 for Ryan Haight Online Pharmacy This addresses online pharmacies by amending the Controlled Substances Act, and it was signed into law in 2008. Conflict of laws in cyberspace is a key impediment for harmonization of legal framework for e-commerce around the world. Many nations accepted the UNCITRAL Model Law on Electronic Commerce (1996) to standardise e-commerce laws worldwide. An informal network of government consumer fair trade agencies came together to form the International Consumer Protection and Enforcement Network (ICPEN) in 1991. Finding strategies to work together to

address consumer issues related to cross-border transactions in products and services, as well as facilitating information sharing among participants for mutual gain and understanding, were the declared goals. This gave rise to Econsumer.gov. An initiative of ICPEN since April 2001. It serves as a reporting gateway for online complaints and associated transactions with overseas businesses. Additionally, the Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) was founded in 1989 with the goal of using free and open trade and investment to bring stability, security, and prosperity to the area. In addition to developing uniform privacy standards for the APEC area, APEC maintains an Electronic Commerce Steering Group. The Australian Competition and Consumer Commission controls and provides guidance on dealing with firms online, as well as specific information on what to do in the event of a problem. In Australia, trade is governed by the Australian Treasury Guidelines for internet commerce. The Financial Services Authority (FSA) used to be the governing body in the United Kingdom. Authority for the majority of the Payment Services Directive (PSD) in the EU, until the Financial Conduct Authority and the Prudential Regulation Authority replaced it in 2013. The Payment Services Regulations 2009 (PSRs), which went into force on November 1, 2009, were the UK's implementation of the PSD. The Information Technology Act 2000 regulates the fundamental applicability of e-commerce in India. The Ministry of Industry and Information Technology (MIIT) is the government agency responsible for overseeing all telecommunications-related operations, including electronic commerce, in China, according to the Telecommunications Regulations of the People's Republic of China, which were established on September 25, 2000. The first administrative rule to address profit-generating operations through the Internet

and establish the framework was the Administrative Measures on Internet Information Services, which was released on the same day. for upcoming laws controlling Chinese e-commerce. According to the amount spent per person, the UK had the largest e-commerce market in the world in 2010. In 2013, the Czech Republic was the European nation where e-commerce contributed the most to the overall income of businesses. Online sales account for about a quarter (24%) of the nation's overall revenue. China's e-commerce presence is growing annually among emerging economies. In the first half of 2015, China's online shopping sales, which accounted for 10% of the country's total consumer retail sales during the same period, hit \$253 billion, with 668 million internet users. Customers now feel more at ease when they shop online thanks to Chinese companies. Trade via e-commerce between China and Other nations had a 32% increase, reaching 2.3 trillion yuan (\$375.8). billion) in 2012, making up 9.6% of China's overall foreign trade. Alibaba held an 80% market share in China's e-commerce industry in 2013. China is the largest online market in the world, with 600 million Internet users in 2014—twice as many as the US. With an estimated US\$899 billion in sales in 2016, China is also the world's largest e-commerce market by value. Brazil's e-commerce industry was expanding rapidly in 2013, and through 2014, retail e-commerce sales are predicted to grow at a robust double-digit rate. Retail e-commerce sales in Brazil were predicted by e-Marketer to reach \$17.3 billion by 2016. As of January 2014, there were approximately 243.2 million internet users in India. Although it has the third-largest user base globally, Although there is not as much Internet penetration as in countries like the US, UK, or France, it is expanding far more quickly, with about 6 million new users joining each month. Cash on delivery is the most popular payment option in India,

accounting for 75% of all e-commerce transactions. Globally, e-commerce has grown to be a crucial tool for both small and large enterprises to engage with and sell to consumers. For the first time ever, e-commerce revenues exceeded \$1 trillion in 2012. E-commerce, also known as mobile commerce or m-commerce, is becoming more and more reliant on mobile devices. According to one estimate, mobile device purchases accounted for 25% of the market in 2014.2017. According to one study, information technology and international e-commerce present traditional firms with a favourable prospect for the quick development and expansion of their businesses. Numerous businesses have made significant financial investments in mobile applications. According to the DeLong and McLean Model, three factors—information system quality, service quality, and user satisfaction—contribute to a successful online firm. Time and location are no longer constraints, and there are more ways to connect with customers worldwide and eliminate pointless middlemen, which lowers costs. One-on-one analysis of large customer data can help achieve a high level of personalisation in the strategic plan, which will fully boost the company's core competitiveness products in company.

Impact on markets and retailers:

Economists have hypothesised that because e-commerce makes it easier for customers to research products and prices, price rivalry should become more intense. According to research conducted by four economists at the University of Chicago, the rise of online shopping has also had an impact on the structure of the book and travel agency industries, two sectors that have seen notable increases in e-commerce. Larger businesses can typically offer lower prices by utilising economies of scale. Only the smallest category of booksellers, those with one to four employees, have deviated

from this tendency, seemingly surviving the trend. E-commerce may change the financial, relational, and procedural switching costs that consumers face, depending on the category. Businesses or individuals engaged in e-commerce, whether purchasers or sellers use technologies connected to the Internet to complete their transactions. E-commerce is well known for its capacity to facilitate business-to-business communication and transactions at any time and location. Through the internet, commerce may be done by anyone, whether they are in the US or abroad. All consumers and enterprises on the planet are now prospective suppliers and customers thanks to the power of e-commerce, which eliminates geographical restrictions. As a result, switching costs and obstacles could change. One excellent example of e-commerce is eBay, where both individuals and companies may list and sell goods worldwide. The supply chain and logistics are the two most important aspects of e-commerce that must be taken into account. Cross-border logistics usually take a few weeks to complete. Considering this Low supply chain service efficiency will significantly lower customer satisfaction. According to some researchers, integrating IT infrastructure and e-commerce expertise could significantly increase a company's overall commercial value. According to another researcher, e-commerce should think about setting up warehousing facilities abroad in order to increase the logistics system's efficiency and boost consumer loyalty in addition to satisfaction.

Impact on supply chain management:

Businesses have long been concerned about disconnect between supply chain technology's advantages and the ways in which those advantages may be realised. The rise of e-commerce, however, has made it possible to distribute the advantages of the new supply chain technologies in a more

efficient and useful manner. The potential of e-commerce to combine both intra- and inter-company tasks means that it may also have an impact on the supply chain's three flows: information, financial, and physical. Businesses' methods of moving goods and products were enhanced by the physical flows. E-commerce maximised the information processing capacity that businesses previously possessed, and it enables them to have more money flows effective settlement and payment options. Furthermore, e-commerce affects supply networks at a more complex level: First, as businesses can use electronic tools to detect gaps between various supply chain levels, the performance gap will be closed; Second, new capabilities like deploying ERP systems like SAP ERP, Xero, or Megaventory have helped businesses manage operations with customers and suppliers as a result of the growth of e-commerce. However, the full potential of these new skills has yet to be realised. Thirdly, because they anticipate a return on their investment, tech companies will continue to make investments in new e-commerce software solutions. Fourth, e-commerce would assist in resolving a number of problems that businesses may find challenging, like cross-border shifts or governmental obstacles. Lastly, e-commerce offers businesses a more effective and efficient method of working together throughout the supply chain.

Social impact:

Virtual enterprise, virtual bank, network marketing, online shopping, payment, and advertising, together with e-commerce and its distinct charm that has gradually emerged, are examples of this new terminology that was previously unheard of but is now as commonplace to people. This illustrates how e-commerce has a significant impact on society and the economy. One industry that is expanding quickly worldwide is business-to-business (B2B),

which lowers costs, boosts economic efficiency, and creates jobs. The following article will discuss six themes to help you understand how e-commerce has impacted the economy and society:

- E-commerce has altered the relative value of time, but it is still important to consider time as a key indication of the nation's economic health.
- E-commerce provides businesses and consumers with the information they require, transforming information into complete transparency. As a result, businesses can no longer employ advertising or space to gain a competitive advantage. Furthermore, theoretically, social welfare will be maximised by perfect rivalry between business and consumer sovereignty.
- In actuality, big businesses usually benefited from information resources at the expense of customers throughout the previous economic activity. These days, consumers' rights are safeguarded by transparent and up-to-date information, as they can utilise the internet to choose the portfolio that best suits their needs. Businesses will be significantly more competitive than they were previously, and as a result, the growth of e-commerce will enhance social welfare.
- Humanistic spirit is also altered by the new economy driven by e-commerce, although employee loyalty is most significantly altered. Because the industry is competitive, the professionalism of the employees becomes essential for the business in the specialised market. The main issue facing businesses is how to strengthen their internal culture and a set of interacting methods. Additionally, even if e-commerce

lowers transaction and information costs, its advancement also makes people overly tech-savvy. An additional initiative for firm development is to emphasise a more humane approach to work. Life is the foundation of everything, and technology is only a tool to help people live better lives.

- Online retailers compile their clients' interests and buying history. Online marketers are using this information to advertise pertinent goods and services. Online customers benefit from more convenience as a result.
- Online goods are easier for customers to find because they can be searched. A review system is provided by many internet merchants to assist customers in selecting the item they want to buy. This adds to the ease and boosts enjoyment.

Technically speaking, e-commerce is not a new business, but it is generating a new economic paradigm. Although most people believe that e-commerce will have a good impact on economic society in the future, it is difficult to predict how it will affect society in the short term. E-commerce has been described as a kind of incorporeal revolution by others. Among the many social advantages of e-commerce are the following: first, compared to operating a physical store, operating an e-commerce business is much less expensive; second, there is no need to pay rent for pricey space; and third, business procedures are streamlined and fewer man-hours are needed to run a typical business efficiently. E-commerce's influence will only grow in the fields of law, education, culture, and policy. E-commerce will genuinely put people at the centre of the society of information.

Distribution Channels:

As businesses have embraced brick-and-click and pure-click channel systems, e-commerce has become more significant. We can differentiate between brick-and-click and pure-click channel systems that businesses use.

- Enterprises that have developed a website without any prior business existence are known as pure-click or pure-play enterprises.
- Existing businesses that have added an online website for e-commerce are known as "bricks-and-clicks" companies.
- Click-to-brick internet merchants who then open physical stores to support their online presence.

Objectives of Study:

The paper has following objectives:

1. To describe the idea of e-commerce.
2. To research the e-commerce opportunities in India
3. To research the different issues that Indian e-commerce faces.
4. To research key elements for India's e-commerce expansion.
5. To research how the Indian economy is affected by e-commerce.
6. To research e-commerce's expansion and impact.

Research Methodology:

The secondary data used in this study was gathered from a variety of online sources, including research papers and publications from the Ministry of Commerce and the Government of India.

Impact of E-Commerce on Indian Economy:**India's prospects in e-commerce:**

As seen in Table 1, the number of internet users in India increased from around 354 million in June 2015 to 462 million in 2016, accounting for 34.8% of the country's total population. E-commerce penetration is low when compared to markets like the United States (266 million, 84%) or France (54 million, 81%), despite having the second-largest user base in the world, only surpassed by China (650 million, 48% of the population). However, it is expanding at an unprecedented rate, adding about 6 million new entrants each month. The industry as a whole agrees that growth is reaching a turning point. Cash on delivery is the most popular payment option in India, accounting for 75% of all e-commerce transactions. International consumer goods, including tail items, are becoming increasingly more in demand quicker than e-commerce and in-country supply from licensed distributors. As of 2015, Flipkart, Snapdeal, Amazon India, and Paytm are the biggest online retailers in India.

- Internet Users in India in 2016 was 462,124,989
- Share of India Population 34.8% (penetration)
- Total Population: 1,326,801,576
- Share of World Internet users: 13.5%
- Internet Users in the world: 3,424,971,237

Internet Users in India

Year	Internet users*	Penetration	Total Population	Non-User (Internetless)	1Year User Change	1Year User Change	Population Change
2016	462,124,989	34.8 %	1,326,801,576	864,676,587	30.5 %	108,010,242	1.2 %
2015	354,114,747	27 %	1,311,050,527	956,935,780	51.9 %	120,962,270	1.22 %
2014	233,152,478	18 %	1,295,291,543	1,062,139,065	20.7 %	39,948,148	1.23 %
2013	193,204,330	15.1 %	1,279,498,874	1,086,294,544	21.5 %	34,243,984	1.26 %
2012	158,960,346	12.6 %	1,263,589,639	1,104,629,293	26.5 %	33,342,533	1.29 %
2011	125,617,813	10.1 %	1,247,446,011	1,121,828,198	36.1 %	33,293,976	1.34 %
2010	92,323,838	7.5 %	1,230,984,504	1,138,660,666	48.5 %	30,157,710	1.38 %
2009	62,166,128	5.1 %	1,214,182,182	1,152,016,054	18.6 %	9,734,457	1.43 %
2008	52,431,671	4.4 %	1,197,070,109	1,144,638,438	12.5 %	5,834,088	1.47 %
2007	46,597,582	4 %	1,179,685,631	1,133,088,049	42.9 %	13,995,197	1.51 %
2006	32,602,386	2.8 %	1,162,088,305	1,129,485,919	19.3 %	5,275,016	1.55 %
2005	27,327,370	2.4 %	1,144,326,293	1,116,998,923	22.8 %	5,067,787	1.59 %
2004	22,259,583	2 %	1,126,419,321	1,104,159,738	19.1 %	3,567,041	1.63 %
2003	18,692,542	1.7 %	1,108,369,577	1,089,677,035	11.5 %	1,926,786	1.67 %
2002	16,765,756	1.5 %	1,090,189,358	1,073,423,602	136.9 %	9,689,725	1.71 %
2001	7,076,031	0.7 %	1,071,888,190	1,064,812,159	27.3 %	1,518,576	1.75 %

- A person who can access the Internet at home using any kind of device and connection is considered an Internet user.
- Source: Live Stats on the Internet
- World Bank, United Nations Population Division, and International Telecommunication Union (ITU) data elaboration.

Market Size and Growth:

The value of India's e-commerce market increased from roughly \$3.9 billion in 2009 to \$12.6 billion in 2013. The e-retail market was valued at US\$2.3 billion in 2013. Travel accounts for almost 70% of India's e-commerce business. Google India estimates that 35 million Indians shopped online in the first quarter of 2014, and by the end of 2016, that number is predicted to rise to 100 million. CAGR in comparison to an 8–10% worldwide growth rate. In terms of sales, the two largest categories are apparel and electronics. The Internet and Mobile Association of India found that in December 2016, the e-commerce industry was worth ₹ 211,005 crore. According to the survey, 61% of the e-commerce business is made up of online travel. India is anticipated to will produce \$100 billion in online retail sales, of which \$35 billion will come from e-commerce in the fashion industry. In the

upcoming years, online clothing sales are expected to increase fourfold. The retail market in India was valued at \$470 billion in 2011, \$675 billion in 2016, and is projected to reach \$850 billion by 2020, with a 10% compound annual growth rate. Forrester predicts that between 2012 and 2016, the e-commerce market in India would expand at the fastest rate in the Asia-Pacific region, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of more than 57%.

According to Avendus Capital's "India Goes Digital" research, the Indian e-commerce sector is projected to grow by Rs 28,500 Crore (\$6.3 billion) in 2011. Today, a significant amount of this sector (87%) is made up of online travel. Over the following four years, the Indian online travel market grew at a rate of 22%, reaching ₹ 54,800 crore (\$12.2 billion) by 2015. By 2015, the total e-commerce market had grown to Rs 1,07,800 crores (US\$24 billion), with e-

tailing and online travel making similar contributions. Mobile and DTH recharges are another significant e-commerce market, with operator websites handling about a million transactions per day. Online medicine, which sells prescription drugs or complementary and alternative therapies, is a relatively young area of e-commerce. There aren't any specific online pharmacies regulations in India, and it is acceptable to sell prescription drugs online as long as you have a valid licence. Over time, luxury goods like jewellery have also seen an increase in online sales. In the next two to three years, the majority of retail brands anticipate at least 20% of their sales to come from online channels.

Closures:

Even though the industry has grown significantly and is predicted to continue growing, many e-commerce businesses have had to deal with extreme pressure to maintain cash flows. However, not every e-commerce website has found success with it. In order to survive, many of them, including Dhingana, Rock.in, Seventy MM, and others, had to shut down or alter their business plans.

Infrastructure:

Although there are numerous hosting firms in India, the most of them are not appropriate for hosting e-commerce because they offer shared hosting that is far less safe and threat-protected. E-commerce requires hosting that is extremely safe, reliable, and secure. With some e-commerce businesses beginning to provide software as a service (SaaS) for running web stores for low one-time prices, trends are shifting. E-commerce marketing can be done in a number of ways, including blogs, forums, search engines, and online advertising platforms like Adroll and Google Adwords. In December 2012, Google India teamed up with e-commerce giants Flipkart, Home Shop18, Snapdeal,

Indiatimes, and others to launch India's own version of Cyber Monday, called the Great Online Shopping Festival Plan my journey. The phrase "Cyber Monday" was created in the United States to describe the Monday following Black Friday, which is the Friday following Thanksgiving. The most recent Great Online Shopping Festival, or GOSF, took place from December 10–12, 2014. Without any advertising activities, Amazon.com started its Amazon India marketplace in early June 2013. After its biggest Indian competitor, Flipkart, announced \$1 billion in funding, Amazon stated in July 2014 that it would invest \$2 billion (₹ 12,000 crore) in India to grow its business. In order to put more pressure on competitors, Amazon pledged to invest an additional \$3 billion in June 2016. Snapdeal and Flipkart With its Kirana, Amazon has also entered the grocery market. It is now operating in Bangalore and plans to expand to Delhi, Mumbai, and other cities and Chennai, where it must contend with fierce competition from Indian entrepreneurs.

Funding:

The following are instances of venture capital firms that have made investments in Indian e-commerce businesses:

It raised almost USD 2.3 billion. Flipkart revealed on July 10, 2013, that it had collected \$200 million from its current investors, which included Tiger Global, Naspers, Accel Partners, and ICONIQ Capital. In addition, the company had raised \$160 million from Dragoneer Investment Group, Morgan Stanley Wealth Management, Sofina, Vulcan Inc., and other investors. In February 2014, a consortium of investors led by Azim Premji, Chairman of Wipro, raised \$50 million for the online apparel store Myntra.com through Premji Invest. Additionally, in May 2014, Flipkart reportedly paid ₹ 2,000 crores to acquire Myntra. Snapdeal and others contributed \$36

million to Pepper Tap's fundraising efforts in September 2015.

Niche retailer:

A number of niche companies that primarily focus on a single theme have emerged as a result of the growth of e-commerce. Over 25% of the 1,06,086 websites that are registered every day are for niche enterprises. Royal Enfield sold 200 special series motorcycles online in 2014. One of the more well-liked verticals, online clothing accounts for 42% of all retail e-commerce sales, along with computers and consumer electronics. Speciality online retailers such as Redwolf, No Nasties, and Headbanger's Merch collaborate with and even support indie performers. Some well-known companies, such as Arvind, are increasingly developing apparel lines just for online retailers. Numerous investment rounds have been obtained by some of the larger online retailers, such as VoxPop Clothing, the most recent Blume Ventures raised \$1 million in a 2014 round. The major

players are gradually acquiring these specialised companies as they gain popularity. Mahindra Retail, a division of the \$17 billion Mahindra Group, purchased Baby Oye. The Godrej Group purchased Ekstop to enhance its offline chain of Nature's Basket stores.

Vertical specific E-Commerce in India:

Because their offerings differ from those of other well-known e-commerce companies, vertical specialised e-tailers concentrate on a specialised product or service. They are able to raise money thanks to the value addition of their venture. This industry-specific risk's crucial component provides an easy-to-use experience that is motivated by cost-effectiveness, convenience, and additional information. For instance, the cab service provider Ola Cabs sets itself apart from the competition by offering customers who are looking for both cab service and auto rentals an excellent, user-friendly experience. India's vertical-specific e-commerce is displayed in Table 2.

Table 2: Vertical specific e-commerce players in India

Travel	Real Estate	Fashion	Furniture	Health	Education
MakemyTrip	MagicBricks	Jabong	FabFurninsh	Healthkart	EduKart
Goibibo	CommonFloor	Myntra	Pepperfry	LensKart	Meritnation
Yatra	99acres	YepMe	Urban Ladder	Portea	Edureka
IRCTC	Housing	Zovi	Zansaar	Medical	Toppr
Cleartrip	ZRICKS	Fashion and You	InLiving	Indianhealthconsultants	embibe

Challenges in e-commerce:

Players from all over the world are taking notice of India's growing e-commerce volumes. With 1.2 billion inhabitants, India is the second most populous nation in the world. To put that figure into perspective, keep in mind that the populations of Germany, the United Kingdom, France, Italy, the Netherlands, Belgium, and Greece combined make up one-fourth of India's total population! India is remains one of the

most alluring rising markets for e-commerce, even with its lower per capita spending power. However, India is far from being a paradise. These are the top eight issues that Indian e-commerce companies deal with.

Indian customers return much of the merchandise they purchase online:

In India, e-commerce attracts a lot of first-time customers. This indicates that they are still unsure of what to anticipate from e-

commerce platforms. Because of this, purchasers are occasionally the victims of aggressive selling. However, they show regret and return the items when the product is delivered. Even though customer regret is a worldwide issue, it is particularly common in nations like India, where a large portion of development is attributed to new customers. Due to the special difficulties in reverse logistics, returns are costly for e-commerce companies. In cross-border e-commerce, this becomes even more complicated.

Cash on delivery is the preferred payment mode:

In India, cash on delivery is the most popular method of payment due to limited credit card usage and low confidence in internet purchases. Manual cash collection is costly, time-consuming, and hazardous in contrast to computerised payments.

Payment gateways have a high failure rate:

Indian payment channels have an exceptionally high failure rate by international standards, as if the preference for cash on delivery wasn't terrible enough. Since many customers do not try to pay again once a transaction fails, e-commerce businesses that use Indian payment gateways are losing sales.

Internet penetration is low:

India's internet penetration rate is still far lower than that of many western nations. Furthermore, in a number of areas, the quality of connectivity is subpar. However, both of these issues are quickly going away. It won't be long before connectivity problems aren't listed among the obstacles facing Indian e-commerce.

Feature phones still rule the roost:

Even though there are a lot of mobile phone users in India overall, the vast

majority still utilise feature phones rather than smartphones. For all intents and purposes, this consumer category cannot make purchases online while on the go. The sharp decline in the cost of entry-level smartphones is a positive indication, even though it will still be a few years before the balance shifts in favour of smartphones. I anticipate that new smartphones priced between \$30 and \$40 will be announced in India throughout the upcoming quarters. That ought to encourage more people to purchase smartphones.

Postal addresses are not standardized:

The logistics provider may probably phone you to enquire about your precise location if you place an online buy in India. Your address is obviously insufficient. This is a result of the lack of uniformity in the writing of postal addresses. Ecommerce logistics concerns are exacerbated by last mile issues.

Logistics is a problem in thousands of Indian towns:

The absence of postal address standardisation is not the only logistical issue facing India. Because of the country's vast expanse, hundreds of towns are difficult to reach. The logistical infrastructure of metropolitan areas and other large urban centres is quite strong. However, the lack of easy access to a sizable percentage of potential clients is a deterrent because the Indian market's true appeal is found in its vast population. The fact that cash on delivery is the primary method of payment in India exacerbates the logistics issue. The government-owned postal services, private Indian businesses, and international logistics providers are working hard to find a solution to the logistics issue. If someone could communicate the enormity of the issue into a chance, the Indian logistics sector may soon be the subject of a noteworthy success story.

Overfunded competitors are driving up cost of customer acquisition:

The e-commerce industry has seen significant investment in recent years due to the thriving Indian start-up scene. Some investors are willing to pay absurdly huge sums of money to gain market share now because the long-term prospects for e-commerce businesses are so promising. The Indian customer has an abundance of options, of course. But now that investors are becoming concerned about going farther down a dangerous slope, this trend has reversed, and I anticipate more sensible behaviour in 2014. Although the subject matter of this post is e-commerce issues in India, which is inherently biased, it is noteworthy that e-commerce behemoths are becoming more and more interested in India. India is seeing an increase in cross-border e-commerce, and numerous major multinational businesses are also investing heavily in this market in establishing a business in India.

Essential Factors for growth of e-commerce in India:

Examining the e-commerce industry is one of the best approaches to obtain income in the current economy. A new method of conducting business that could generate profits at a reduced cost was presented to merchants with the introduction of the Internet. However, a lot has changed in recent years, and now more than ever, online retailers may quickly create an e-commerce website and increase their online visibility. These five crucial pointers can help e-commerce businesses succeed and stay in business for a long time.

Harness the Power of Social Networking Websites:

Merchants now have a completely new approach to communicate with potential clients and market themselves thanks to the social revolution of the Internet that has

taken place in recent years. Participate in social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter to build brand awareness and buzz. You can advertise your products on dozens of internet marketplaces, some of which fee for their services and others of which are free. Be present in as many online locations as you can.

Know the Economics of your Business:

A solid grasp of your company's economics and how expenses will impact your bottom line is essential to your success. How would your profit margins be impacted, for instance, if you decide to advertise a product on a specific online marketplace? To guarantee revenues, you must comprehend and effectively handle your funds.

Be Transparent:

Sensible online shoppers only want to deal with safe, trustworthy online merchants because of the skyrocketing rate of online credit card fraud. As a result, you need to be open and honest about your company. Providing customers with information about you and your company will help you gain their trust and give you a sense of legitimacy. Provide thorough client support and safe payment processing.

Make Customer Service a Priority:

Even though customer service provided by an online retailer will undoubtedly differ from that of a physical store, it is still a crucial part of any profitable enterprise. While negative customer service seems to spread more fast, positive customer service can spread swiftly as well. Make sure that all of your interactions with clients are pleasant and engaging, and that you provide them with a variety of choices, such as email assistance and a working toll-free number.

Re-evaluate your Payment Processing:

Without going over budget, make sure you are still getting the most out of your payment processing provider. This is particularly important if you wish to support worldwide payments and grow abroad. Make sure your current offerings are still a suitable fit for your website by speaking with a customer service representative from your provider.

Customer convenience:

By offering them the opportunity to pay with cash on delivery.

Replacement guarantee:

Customers should be given a 30-day replacement warranty.

Reach:

Facilitating M-Commerce services and making websites mobile-friendly.

Location based services:

Promoting the correct product at the right time and place becomes crucial because today's consumers are constantly on the go.

Multiple payment option:

There should be options for bank payments, debit cards, and standard credit cards.

Right content:

For users on the go, it is crucial to have the correct content and target clients with clear and pertinent information.

Price comparison:

Instant price comparison providers are quite well-liked by budget-conscious consumers.

Shipment option:

There should be a cheap shipment. After work, it should be convenient to pick up orders on the way home.

Logistical challenges:

The geographical dispersion of India presents logistical difficulties. Logistics strategy should be based on the types of items that providers are offering.

Legal challenges:

There should be legal requirement of generating invoices for online transactions.

Quick Service:

The business offers prompt service.

Terms and condition:

Clear and reasonable terms and conditions are essential.

Quality:

The quality of the products should match what is displayed on the portal.

Customer care centre:

There should be a dedicated customer service centre open around-the-clock.

Conclusion:

The idea behind e-commerce is to use the Internet to do business more efficiently and effectively. It involves allowing clients to serve themselves and granting them controlled access to your computer systems. It involves integrating your website with the core of your business and dedicating your organisation to a significant online endeavour. India will have between 30 and 70 million Internet users, which is on par with or even more than many developed nations. India's internet economy will then have greater significance. E-commerce is expected to play a significant role in the twenty-first century due to the internet's rapid expansion, and both small and large businesses will be able to take advantage of the new opportunities that will arise. The government's function is to establish a legal framework for e-commerce that ensures fundamental rights like consumer protection, intellectual property, privacy, and fraud prevention are all protected while allowing both domestic and foreign trade to grow. We discovered a variety of options for producers, wholesalers/distributors, retailers, and individuals. Retailers should always be in contact with their customers and fulfil electronic orders. Through e-commerce,

wholesalers can benefit from those who can sign agreements with reputable manufacturers and connect their company with the internet. By having a brand identity and providing improved information about their products to the other links in the supply chain, producers may also connect with consumers online. There is a growing need for establishments that offer internet access or cyber cafes as more individuals connect through e-commerce. As a result, anyone who wants to use it can create a cyber-network and reap the rewards. People could find a variety of job opportunities. Expert opinions and the aforementioned research indicated that, provided the necessary conditions were met, e-commerce in India will have a promising future in the years to come.

References:

1. Bansal, Rashmi, Growth of the Electronic Commerce in China and India: A Comparative Study
2. Chaudhury, Abijit; Jean-Pierre Kuilboer (2002). EBusinessand e-Commerce Infrastructure.

3. Ranjan, K. R. Future of E Commerce and Online Shopping in India.
4. MK, Euro Info Correspondence Centre (Belgrade, Serbia), "E-commerce-Factor of Economic Growth."
5. Sinha (April 2009), "Ecommerce in India – The Real Challenges
6. Zorayda Ruth Andam (2003) "e-Commerce and e-Business" in e-ASEAN task force.
7. Websites: E-Commerce Guide.Com, E-Commerce Times, www.business.com, www.forrester.com,
8. www.iamai.in
9. <http://www.manjeetss.com/articles/advantagesdisadvantagesecommerce.htm>
10. <http://www.manjeetss.com/articles/advantagesdisadvantagesecommerce.html>
11. <http://www.manjeetss.com/articles/advantagesdisadvantagesecommerce.html>